

Effectiveness of warm water foot bath vs tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in selected hospitals of the city

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ABSTRACT: -

INTRODUCTION: Changes in body temperature can cause the body's organs and enzyme systems to function abnormally. There are several reasons and mechanisms why anesthesia patients are susceptible to temperature fluctuations. The range of heat-related ailments is from minor to severe. Heat rash and heat cramps are mild heat-related ailments that typically go away with rest or at-home remedies. However, to prevent major problems, moderate or severe heat-related disorders, such as heat exhaustion and heat stroke, need to be treated right away. A child's body temperature can be lowered more successfully with a sponge bath. By using a warm wash cloth to wipe a child's entire body, the sponge bath technique effectively uses heat evaporation to provide hydrotherapy besides reducing the amount of cold water that the body comes into contact with.

METHOD: - The present study is Quantitative Research with, Quasi-experimental two group pre-test-posttest design. In this study, Researchers have adopted a Quantitative approach for Effectiveness of warm water foot bath vs tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in selected hospitals of the city. 60 samples were selected 30 samples were taken in each experimental group by using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. The sample was chosen based on specific inclusion criteria from the selected hospitals.

RESULT:

Analysis of data related to the temperature of children diagnosed with hyperthermia before intervention

In the warm water foot bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In the Tepid sponge bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test.

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

In the warm water foot bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In posttest1 (30 minutes), 30% of them had low pyrexia and 70% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest2 (45

minutes), 10% of them had normal body temperature, 43.3% of them had low pyrexia and 46.7% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest3 (60 minutes), 40% of them had normal body temperature, 20% of them had low pyrexia and 40% of them had moderate pyrexia. This indicates that there is a remarkable reduction in body temperature after a warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. Researchers applied a Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot baths among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. In the warm water foot bath group, in the pre-test, average body temperature was 101.1oF which was reduced to 100.6oF, 100° F, and 99.5° F in pottest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes) and pottest3 (60 minutes) among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. T-values for this test were 11.8, 22.2, and 19.2 with 29 degrees of freedom at post-test1, post-test2 and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. Average body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia reduced significantly in post-tests as compared to that in pre-test. The warm water foot bath is significantly effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

In the tepid sponge bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In posttest1 (30 minutes), 33.3% of them had low pyrexia and 66.7% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest2 (45 minutes), 30% of them had normal body temperature, 50% of them had low pyrexia and 20% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest3 (60 minutes), 80% of them had normal body temperature and 20% of them had low pyrexia. This indicates that there is a remarkable reduction in body temperature after a tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. Researchers applied Paired t-test for the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. In the tepid sponge bath group, in the pre-test, the average body temperature was 101.1oF which was reduced to 100.3oF, 99.4oF and 98.5oF in pottest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and pottest3 (60 minutes) among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. T-values for this test were 21.6, 17.9, and 18.6 with 29 degrees of freedom at post-test1, post-test2, and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. Average body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia reduced significantly in post-tests as compared to that in pre-test. The tepid sponge bath is significantly effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Analysis of data related to the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath in reducing hyperthermia among children

The researcher applied two sample z-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot baths and tepid sponge baths in reducing hyperthermia among children. In the warm water foot bath group, the average reduction in body temperature was 0.46, 0.56, and 0.55 in post-test1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). In the tepid sponge bath group, the average reduction in body temperature was 0.74, 0.91, and 0.89 in posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes) and post-test3 (60 minutes). Z-values for this test were 8.22, 6.94 and 7.16 at post-test1, post-test2 and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected.

The average reduction in body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in the tepid sponge bath group was significantly more than that in the warm water foot bath group at posttest1 (30 minutes), posttest2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). The tepid sponge bath is significantly more effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia as compared to the warm water foot bath.

Analysis of data related to the association of selected demographic variables and body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

Since p-values corresponding to age were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable age was found to have a significant association among the children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

CONCLUSION: -. The data was gathered using descriptive and inferential statistics. And tepid sponge bath was significant in reducing body temperature, whereas, demographic variables was found significant association among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

INTRODUCTION:

Changes in body temperature can cause the body's organs and enzyme systems to function abnormally. There are several reasons and mechanisms why anesthesia patients are susceptible to temperature fluctuations. The hypothalamus mediates thermoregulation, which keeps the body's normal temperature within a specific range. Hypothermia is a typical side effect of general anesthesia. The mechanisms include decreased thermoregulation brought on by anesthesia, which results in vasodilation, inhibits vasoconstriction, lowers metabolic rate, and exposes the body to cold environments.

The range of heat-related ailments is from minor to severe. Heat rash and heat cramps are mild heat-related ailments that typically go away with rest or at-home remedies. However, to prevent major problems, moderate or severe heat-related disorders, such as heat exhaustion and heat stroke, need to be treated right away.

The hydrotherapeutic technique is hot water foot bath therapy, which produces a calming and healing effect while also improving temperature, encouraging muscular relaxation, relieving pain, dilating blood vessels, and promoting circulation. By stimulating the immune system and White Blood Cells, Hot water foot bath therapy is supposed to treat the underlying infection.

Tepid sponge care, which is typically administered to clients with high hyperthermia, increases body temperature management by evaporation and conduction. This action aims to lower the body temperature of clients with symptoms of hyperthermia.

A child's body temperature can be lowered more successfully with a sponge bath. By using a warm wash cloth to wipe a child's entire body, the sponge bath technique effectively uses heat evaporation to provide hydrotherapy besides reducing the amount of cold water that the body comes into contact with.¹

METHODS:

The present study is Quantitative Research with, Quasi-experimental two group pre-test-posttest design. In this study, Researchers have adopted a Quantitative approach for Effectiveness of warm water foot bath vs tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in selected hospitals of the city. 60 samples were selected 30 samples were taken in each experimental group by using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. The sample was chosen based on specific inclusion criteria from the selected hospitals. The research tool comprised of demographic data and a self-prepared temperature recording data sheet. An informed consent regarding their willingness to participate in the study was given to parents of each willing participants. Before any data was collected, the researcher allayed the parent's concerns about the study. The demographic information of the child using standardized questionnaires was collected by the researcher and additionally, the researcher assessed the effectiveness of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath on hyperthermia by using a self-prepared temperature checklist for recording data. To enlighten the parents about their children's rights, with every sample, the researcher had taken the necessary amount of time where the willingness of each sample was given preference.²

Study Design: pre-test-posttest design.

Setting: Selected hospitals of city

Sampling Technique: non-probability convenient sampling technique.

Population: children diagnosed with hyperthermia

Method of data collection:

- Approval from the research committee member and written permission will be obtained from the head of the institution to conduct research.
- Selection of sample with non-probability convenient sampling technique.
- The researcher will explain the purpose of the research to the samples.
- The researcher will obtain informed consent from samples.
- Assess the selected demographic variables in both experimental groups.
- After the intervention of the Warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath on selected demographic variables, it will be reassessed in 30 minutes, 45 minutes, and 1 hour among samples.

Description of the tool

The tool consists of two parts:

Part 1: Assent form

Part 2: Tool

Section A: Demographic variables

Section B: Temperature recording checklist

DESCRIPTION OF INTERVENTION

1. First, the researcher establishes a good relationship with the child and introduces the research topic to the caregivers. The researcher will collect data on demographic variables.
2. The researcher explained everything about the warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath procedure (Definition, equipment, and description of steps).
3. The researcher monitored the sample temperature before performing the procedure.
4. The researcher will perform the procedure
5. After the procedure monitor the sample temperature using a digital thermometer.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution will be used to describe demographic variables.

Mean and standard deviation will be used to analyze the pre-test and post-test selected demographic variables and hyperthermia among the children.

Inferential statistics: Paired t-test will be used to compare the pre-test and post-test hyperthermia among the experimental group.

The chi-square test will be used to associate with hyperthermia among patients undergoing warm water foot baths and tepid sponge baths with their selected demographic variables.

Data Analysis:**Sample Size:**

For the study sample size will be 60.³

The formula used for sample size is-

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2,$$

Where, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (e.g. for a confidence level of 95%, α is 0.05 and the critical value is 1.96), MOE is the margin of error, p is the prevalence

For our calculations,

$$Z_{\alpha/2}=1.96$$

$$P= 0.15$$

$$MOE= 0.14$$

The sample size, n comes to be 25. Select 30 samples in each group.

Sampling Criteria:

- **Inclusion Criteria:** Hospitalized children with fever ranging from 99°-103° F.
- Children in the age group of 3-12 years.
- Children receiving only antipyretic and no other physical or external measures for lowering body temperature.
- Parents giving consent for the intervention.⁴
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Children who develop rigor before or during the intervention.
- Children who are contraindicated for sponging like burns, head injuries, septicemia, or open wounds.
- Children who are unconscious.
- Children who are seriously ill.⁴

RESULTS:

Description of samples based on their demographic characteristics.

- **Age**
In Warm water Foot bath group, 40% of the children diagnosed with hyperthermia had age 3-5 years, 26.7% of them had age 5.1-8 years and 33.3% of them had age 8.1-12 years. In Tepid sponge bath group, 33.3% of the children diagnosed with hyperthermia had age 3-5 years, 36.7% of them had age 5.1-8 years and 30% of them had age 8.1-12 years
- **Gender**
In the Warm water Foot bath and tepid sponge bath group, 50% of them were males and 50% of them were females.
- **Duration of hospitalization**
In the Warm water Foot bath group, 23.3% of them had hospitalization since one day, 36.7% of them were hospitalized for two days, 13.3% of them have been hospitalized for three days and 26.7% of them had hospitalization for three days and more. In the Tepid sponge bath group, 33.3% of them had hospitalization for one day, 30% of them were hospitalized for two days, 26.7% of them were hospitalized for three days and 10% of them had hospitalization for three days or more. □ **Symptoms of fever**

In the Warm water Foot bath group, 26.7% of them had chills, 20% of them had a rigor, 23.3% of them had fatigue, 20% of them had body pain, 6.7% of them had headaches and 3.3% of them had red patches. In the Tepid sponge bath group, 40% of them had chills, 13.3% of them had a rigor, 13.3% of them had fatigue, 26.7% of them had body pain, 3.3% of them had headache and 3.3% of them had red patches.

Section II

Analysis of data related to the temperature of children diagnosed with hyperthermia before intervention

In the warm water foot bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In the Tepid sponge bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test.

Section III

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

In the warm water foot bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In posttest1 (30 minutes), 30% of them had low pyrexia and 70% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest2 (45 minutes), 10% of them had normal body temperature, 43.3% of them had low pyrexia and 46.7% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest3 (60 minutes), 40% of them had normal body temperature, 20% of them had low pyrexia and 40% of them had moderate pyrexia. This indicates that there is a remarkable reduction in body temperature after a warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. Researchers applied a Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot baths among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. In the warm water foot bath group, in the pre-test, average body temperature was 101.1oF which was reduced to 100.6oF, 100° F, and 99.5° F in posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes) and posttest3 (60 minutes) among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. T-values for this test were 11.8, 22.2, and 19.2 with 29 degrees of freedom at post-test1, post-test2 and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. Average body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia reduced significantly in post-tests as compared to that in pre-test. The warm water foot bath is significantly effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

In the tepid sponge bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In posttest1 (30 minutes), 33.3% of them had low pyrexia and 66.7% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest2 (45 minutes), 30% of them had normal body temperature, 50% of them had low pyrexia and 20% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest3 (60 minutes), 80% of them had normal body temperature and 20% of them had low pyrexia. This indicates that there is a remarkable reduction in body temperature after a tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. Researchers applied Paired t-test for the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. In the tepid sponge bath group, in the pre-test, the average body temperature was 101.1oF which was reduced to 100.3oF, 99.4oF and 98.5oF in posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and posttest3

(60 minutes) among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. T-values for this test were 21.6, 17.9, and 18.6 with 29 degrees of freedom at post-test1, post-test2, and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. Average body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia reduced significantly in post-tests as compared to that in pre-test. The tepid sponge bath is significantly effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Section V

Analysis of data related to the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath in reducing hyperthermia among children

The researcher applied two sample z-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot baths and tepid sponge baths in reducing hyperthermia among children. In the warm water foot bath group, the average reduction in body temperature was 0.46, 0.56, and 0.55 in post-test1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). In the tepid sponge bath group, the average reduction in body temperature was 0.74, 0.91, and 0.89 in posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes) and post-test3 (60 minutes). Z-values for this test were 8.22, 6.94 and 7.16 at post-test1, post-test2 and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average reduction in body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in the tepid sponge bath group was significantly more than that in the warm water foot bath group at posttest1 (30 minutes), posttest2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). The tepid sponge bath is significantly more effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia as compared to the warm water foot bath.

Section VI

Analysis of data related to the association of selected demographic variables and body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

Since p-values corresponding to age were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable age was found to have a significant association among the children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Conclusion

The study was based on the Ernestine Wiedenbachs prescriptive was used, were Quasiexperimental two-group pre-test and post-test design. The study population consisted of children who were admitted to selected hospitals. A total of 60 samples consisting of 30 samples were taken in each experimental group, by probability convenient sampling technique. For generating necessary data, Content validation was done by 11 experts from different fields. The data was collected from 23/12/2024 to 11/01/2025. Sample were selected according to the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria thus parents were introduced by the investigator, explained the purpose of the study and assured about the confidentiality of the information between the investigator and the respondent. Before data collection consent was taken from the parent. Data was collected from 60 samples from selected hospitals of the city. Findings were recorded according to the tool. The data was gathered using descriptive and inferential statistics. And tepid sponge bath was significant in reducing body temperature, whereas, demographic variables was found significant association among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

DISCUSSION:

The discussion concludes the research report. A thoughtful discussion section clarifies the meaning of the research finding. The most crucial component of every study report is this one. The results of the current study have been described in relation to the research problem's aim, and the researcher has also discussed the study's findings in relation to the outcome objective. The present study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of warm water foot bath vs tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in selected hospitals of the city. The review of literature was done and sample size, study design, etc. was determined. The study approach used was quantitative approach, study design used was quasi experimental two group pre-test post-test design.

The study included children diagnosed with hyperthermia, total 60 samples were selected using Non probability, convenient sampling technique; 30 samples were placed in both experimental groups. Tools were selected for collection of data which included self-structured temperature measuring scale. Validity of tool was performed by experts and reliability was done. The tool was found to be valid and reliable. Ethical permission was taken from the ethical committee. Pilot study was done on 10 samples. Analysis of pilot study depicted that the research was feasible to perform. Before main data collection consent was taken by explaining the purpose of research and assurance of confidentiality was given to them.

The pre-test of both groups was collected on day one. Intervention of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath was given to the participants placed in experimental groups. Warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath was given to them and was asked to preform once every day for 28 days. Diary was maintained by the participants of experimental group which depicted number of interventions taken by the participants. After intervention post-test was collected from both experimental group.

The master sheet of the data was prepared. Analysis of the study was done using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The data was tabulated; graphs and charts of the data were prepared. Paired't' test and unpaired t' test were used to find the association of level of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath between the groups. And Chi- square test was used to find the association between warm water foot bath vs tepid sponge bath with demographic variables. The result of the study depicted those having hyperthermia among children in experimental group, the children in the experimental group after the applying warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath with hyperthermia in the experimental group 2 had change in temperature.

ABBREVIATIONS:

Sr. No	Abbreviation	Meanings
1	M	Mean
2	SD	Standard deviation
3	f	Frequency
4	df	Degree of freedom
5	t	t-value
6	N	Sample size
7	CVI	Content validity index

Table 2: Temperature of children diagnosed with hyperthermia before intervention

N=30, 30

Timepoint	Body Temperature	Warm water foot bath		Tepid sponge bath	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
Pre-test	Normal	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Low pyrexia	3	10.0%	3	10.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	27	90.0%	27	90.0%

Graph – 2.1

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of samples according to Temperature of children diagnosed with hyperthermia before intervention

In the warm water foot bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test.

In Tepid sponge bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in pre-test.

Section III

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

Table 3: Effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

N=30,

Time point	Body Temperature	Warm water foot bath	
		Freq	%
Pre-test	Normal	0	0.0%
	Low pyrexia	3	10.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	27	90.0%
Post-test1	Normal	0	0.0%
	Low pyrexia	9	30.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	21	70.0%
Post-test2	Normal	3	10.0%
	Low pyrexia	13	43.3%
	Moderate pyrexia	14	46.7%
Post-test3	Normal	12	40.0%
	Low pyrexia	6	20.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	12	40.0%

Graph 3.1

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of samples according to Effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

In the warm water foot bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In posttest1 (30 minutes), 30% of them had low pyrexia and 70% of

them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest2 (45 minutes), 10% of them had normal body temperature, 43.3% of them had low pyrexia and 46.7% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest3 (60 minutes), 40% of them had normal body temperature, 20% of them had low pyrexia and 40% of them had moderate pyrexia. This indicates that there is a remarkable reduction in body temperature after a warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Table 3.2: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

N=30

Time point	Mean(°F)	SD	t	df	p-value
Pre-test	101.1	0.9			
Post-test1	100.6	0.9	11.8	29	0.0000
Post-test2	100.0	0.9	22.2	29	0.0000
Post-test3	99.5	0.9	19.2	29	0.0000

Graph 3.2

Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

Researchers applied a Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot baths among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. In the warm water foot bath group, in the pre-test, average body temperature was 101.1oF which was reduced to 100.6oF, 100 oF, and 99.5 oF in posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes) and posttest3 (60 minutes) among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. T-values for this test were 11.8, 22.2, and 19.2 with 29 degrees of freedom at post-test1, post-test2 and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. Average body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia reduced significantly in post-tests as compared to that in pre-test. The warm water foot bath is significantly effective in reducing the body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

Table 4: Effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia N=30

Time point	Body Temperature	Tepid sponge bath	
		Freq	%
Pre-test	Normal	0	0.0%
	Low pyrexia	3	10.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	27	90.0%
Post-test1	Normal	0	0.0%
	Low pyrexia	10	33.3%
	Moderate pyrexia	20	66.7%
Post-test2	Normal	9	30.0%
	Low pyrexia	15	50.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	6	20.0%
Post-test3	Normal	24	80.0%
	Low pyrexia	6	20.0%
	Moderate pyrexia	0	0.0%

Temperature of children diagnosed with hyperthermia over time in tepid sponge bath group

Graph 4.1

In the tepid sponge bath group, 10% of children diagnosed with hyperthermia had low pyrexia and 90% of them had moderate pyrexia in the pre-test. In posttest1 (30 minutes), 33.3% of them had low pyrexia and 66.7% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest2 (45 minutes), 30% of them had normal body temperature, 50% of them had low pyrexia and 20% of them had moderate pyrexia. In posttest3 (60 minutes), 80% of them had normal body temperature and only 20% of them had low pyrexia. This indicates that there is a remarkable reduction in body temperature after a tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Table 4.1: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia

N=30

Time point	Mean (°F)	SD	t	df	p-value
Pre-test	101.1	0.9			
Post-test1	100.3	0.8	21.6	29	0.0000
Post-test2	99.4	0.6	17.9	29	0.0000
Post-test3	98.5	0.5	18.6	29	0.0000

Graph 4.2

Researchers applied Paired t-test for the effectiveness of tepid sponge bath among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. In the tepid sponge bath group, in the pre-test, average body temperature was 101.1°F which was reduced to 100.3°F, 99.4°F and 98.5°F in posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and posttest3 (60 minutes) among children diagnosed with hyperthermia. T-values for this test were 21.6, 17.9, and 18.6 with 29 degrees of freedom at post-test 1, post-test 2, and post-test 3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. Average body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia reduced significantly in post-tests as compared to that in pre-test. The tepid sponge bath is significantly effective in reducing body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia.

Section V

Analysis of data related to the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath in reducing hyperthermia among children

Table 5: Two sample z-test for the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot bath and tepid sponge bath in reducing hyperthermia among children

N=30, 30

Time point	Warm water foot bath		Tepid sponge bath		z	pvalue
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Posttest1	0.46	0.21	0.74	0.19	8.22	0.000
Posttest2	0.56	0.14	0.91	0.28	6.94	0.000
Posttest3	0.55	0.16	0.89	0.26	7.16	0.000

Graph 5.1

The researcher applied two-sample z-tests to compare the effectiveness of warm water foot baths and tepid sponge baths in reducing hyperthermia among children. In the warm water foot bath group, the average reduction in body temperature was 0.46, 0.56, and 0.55 in post-test1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). In the tepid sponge bath group, the average reduction in body temperature was 0.74, 0.91, and 0.89 in post-test1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). Z-values for this test were 8.22, 6.94 and 7.16 at post-test1, post-test2 and post-test3. Corresponding p-values were small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average reduction in body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia in the tepid sponge bath group was significantly more than that in the warm water foot bath group at posttest1 (30 minutes), post-test2 (45 minutes), and post-test3 (60 minutes). It is evident that the tepid sponge bath is significantly more effective in reducing body temperature among children diagnosed with hyperthermia as compared to warm water foot baths.

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